

PATHWAYS FOR THE WIDESPREAD IMPLEMENTATION OF SUPERADOBE HOUSING IN PUERTO RICO

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ABSTRACT

Puerto Rico is undergoing a housing crisis that has been exacerbated by the aftereffects of Hurricane María and the effects of the climate crisis. Superadobe housing presents a viable material alternative for resilient, safe and accessible housing in the face of these conditions. Plenitud PR- an NGO with a focus on sustainability education- has developed an educational model to address the challenges in the widespread implementation of earthbag housing on the island. The model consists of two educational pathways: one professionally oriented for building professionals, and another oriented for DIY builders.

KEYWORDS

Superadobe; education; accessible housing

INTRODUCTION

Puerto Rico is an archipelago located in X lat and X long. Its geographical characteristics make it exposed to several natural hazards such as hurricanes and earthquakes. These geographical characteristics, combined with other economic and socio-political circumstances make Puerto Rico especially vulnerable to the effects of the climate crisis (Aponte-González, 2013). The economic and socio-political conditions increase the vulnerability of citizens to respond and prepare for natural hazards, which increases the probability of these hazards turning into large-scale human disasters (ProAct network, 2008). Puerto Ricans have been experiencing that throughout the past years, in the aftermath of Hurricane María in 2017 and the earthquakes of 2020. These natural hazards have had catastrophic consequences when combined with other human-made disasters on the island such as the housing crisis. The aftereffects of Hurricane María highlighted the urgency to take adaptive and responsive measures for disaster risk mitigation and management.

In the context of housing, environmental and socio-economic vulnerabilities must be taken into account to develop responsive solutions. On the island, cement production accounts for 8.5% of process related greenhouse gas emissions (Environmental Protection Agency, 2022). Additionally, unregulated conventional construction is threatening natural resources and ecosystems all over the island (Rodríguez-Velázquez & Sosa-Pascual, 2022). These situations highlight the importance of shifting industry paradigms towards practices that lessen environmental impact and aim to protect natural resources.

However, construction is one of the most important economic industries in Puerto Rico. Its value has increased throughout the years as the island enters its 16th year of economic recession (hunter college pdf). Currently, 43.1% of people on the island are unemployed (United States Census, 2021). These factors have heightened the effects of the ongoing housing crisis, which is expected to worsen as displacement increases due to the rippling effects of Act 20/22 (Murphy-Marcos & Mazzei, 2022). These conditions highlight the need for construction that is robust enough to withstand natural hazards, and that also contributes to climate resiliency by addressing these other environmental and socio-economic factors.

Bioconstruction

Bioconstruction is a term that refers to styles and techniques that integrate structures with their surroundings to reduce their environmental impact. This term encompasses a variety of passive design strategies and construction materials that can be implemented to meet the goal of a reduced impact. Superadobe is one construction technique that falls under this denomination. This technique uses a stabilized soil mix within polypropylene bags that are horizontally stacked. The soil mix within the bags is the main structural material, which is stabilized chemically with cement and mechanically through compaction (Canadell, Blanco, & Cavalaro, 2016). The bags serve as formwork to hold the soil materials in place and provide protection during curing. These courses are also reinforced with barbed wire, which increases friction between the bags. Superadobe structures, domes in particular, are extremely robust in the face of environmental loads like the ones generated by hurricanes and earthquakes. The robustness of the domes is due to the arched geometry of the structures, which is self-supporting (Kamal & Rahman, 2018). Barbed wire adds another level of sheer resistance in the face of lateral loads.

Figure 1: Parts of the construction of a superadobe dome. Clockwise: workers filling polypropylene bags; skylight of dome; workers finishing final courses of a dome; a worker laying the barbed wire between courses.

Superadobe construction materials are also more economically accessible than conventional materials (Belofsky & Zemskova, 2018). This type of construction can also contribute to shifting towards a bioeconomy on the island. The holistic approach taken during the designing and building of these structures encompasses sustainable development, climate action, social inclusion and a generation of new value chains for regional development. In comparison to conventional construction, superadobe construction has a lesser environmental impact as it reduces waste generation, lessens demand for non-

renewable energy sources, uses environmentally-friendly products and locally supplied materials and decreases energy consumption due to superior thermal and insulation qualities (Belofsky & Zemskova, 2018) . However, there are several challenges for the widespread implementation of this construction method: clash with constructive local culture, limitation of local trained professionals on the technique, and permitting and licensing issues. A model proposed by Belofsky and Zemskova indicates a three ties approach for implementation centered on building grassroots support, training a professional class and rural village builders and government acceptance (Belofsky & Zemskova, 2018). On the island, Plenitud PR is tackling these challenges through their educational model.

Plenitud PR

Plenitud PR is a nonprofit organization in Las Marías, Puerto Rico. Its mission is to advance access to food, clean water and safe housing for residents of Las Marías and surrounding towns. The organization has spent more than a decade educating communities and peoples of all kinds on sustainable practices from a permaculture ecological perspective. It meets its mission through community educational programs and services from their farm and headquarters. The organization has five programs; three are focused on areas of sustainability and capacity building for technical skills, while the other two focus on serving the elders and children of Las Marías through direct community programming (Figure de la florecita).

Figure 2: Plenitud PR programs diagram.

The educational model at Plenitud PR consists of three tiers (1, 2, & 3) (Figure del infographic de los tiers). Each tier encompasses a different level of depth and mentorship. Tier 1 is the most wide reaching, with a focus on broader engagement. Through social media, conferences and introductory workshops it seeks to generate interest and engage local participation. Tier 2 consists of intensive workshops that are held over multiple days or weeks and aim to give participants a solid base and preparation on the subject at hand. Finally, tier 3 are mentorship programs that occur through guidance on business development, instructor training and stipend support for participants. The tiers have been structured so participants gain more dominion over the subjects and develop leadership skills throughout the process. The outcomes of this educational process have resulted in community leaders, members of Plenitud PR staff, business owners and instructors being better equipped to serve in their fields.

Figure 3: Plenitud PR educational model.

PATHWAYS

The bioconstruction program at Plenitud PR began in 2012. The mission of the program is to advance safe and accessible housing on the island through bioconstruction practices. The organization is currently partnered with Cal-Earth and has offered certified professional training opportunities in superadobe for people on the island. The program has been able to impact nearly 500 people: # through tier 1, # through tier 2 and # through tier 3. The educational structure of the program has been designed to tackle the challenges for implementation through two educational pathways: one for construction industry professionals and another for DIY builders.

Opportunities for construction professionals

Over the past few years, Plenitud PR has shifted focus towards generating more mentorship opportunities for professionals in the construction industry like engineers and architects. The aim of this pathway is to empower these professionals to create more projects employing bioconstruction design methods that help shift conventional practices in the industry. One of these internships- *Design in Bioconstruction*- was hosted during the months of June and July of 2020.

Through a series of online lectures, young professionals were introduced to the principles of bioconstruction and its diverse branches, with a focus on superadobe construction. A total of 65 candidates submitted form applications. However, only 5 could be selected for the workshop component. This educational model was designed with the goal of furthering wide-spread awareness of superadobe

through the experience of the professionals entering the fields of architecture and engineering, where processes for acquiring construction permits, planning and designing adequate structures are essential to solidifying superadobe as a viable alternative under the rules of regulations of construction in Puerto Rico. The structure of the *Design in Bioconstruction* internship consisted of a (3) days-a-week workshop where young professionals partnered with other professionals with prior experience in the bioconstruction field, and weekend conferences, for 10 weeks. By the end of the internship, participants had completed the design of a reception office structure that incorporated bioconstruction design principles, a master plan of Plenitud PR farms, where they incorporated permaculture design principles with bioconstruction for future development, and two new structures designed for future housing, increasing Plenitud PR's hosting capabilities. For this workshop series, assessment for participants was evaluated through pass/fail.

Like many of the workshops and courses Plenitud PR has offered in recent years, COVID-19 restrictions have played an important role in how the educational model is designed. This internship was offered during the peak of COVID-19 cases. This meant that the internship was offered through virtual platforms, such as Google Meets. However, this granted the opportunity to open the weekend lectures to all participants who had submitted applications prior to the final selection. Each lecture averaged from 45-50 participants, all of which are active or soon to be entering both architecture and engineering fields. As for the workshop component, the 5-participant limit offered a more hands-on and focused teaching dynamic for the interns. This was necessary to have a successful internship given the limiting interactions offered through virtual learning.

Developing and putting into practice this educational model served as an important step towards standardizing superadobe architecture in Puerto Rico in the face of a very rigid and traditional construction practice. Despite the limitations put in place during this time, participants left with a strong sense of understanding of the principles of bioconstruction and superadobe as a construction technique. Many of the 65 overall applicants have returned to the newer workshops and some have worked directly with Plenitud PR and other bioconstruction professionals in the development of new projects. These include the development of various superadobe model houses outside of the dome structure, such as in the form of a vault, to create a catalog of available superadobe houses that the public could purchase plans for. These types of structures are designed to have an orthogonal floor plan layout that could be easily understood by newcomers who are learning about superadobe (Figure 4). A vaulted roof superadobe structure was also designed to be built on Plenitud PR's farm to increase the farm's housing capabilities. This model is currently undergoing the traditional permit acquisition process that regulates all constructions done in Puerto Rico. When it acquires all permits, it will be the first of its kind to do so. Some participant graduates have also taught in a few of the recent superadobe workshops and online lectures Plenitud PR has offered. As for the participants, this educational model allowed individuals to network with others who share similar interests in new ways to build and create architecture.

a) Floor plan of a superadobe vault.

b) Render of the outside view of a superadobe vault.

Figure 4: Renders created by a participant of the *Design in Bioconstruction Intership*.

Opportunities for DIY Builders

The educational opportunities for D.I.Y. builders focus on training people with diverse backgrounds on bioconstruction techniques that they can employ without previous construction knowledge or experience. In January of 2021, the *Professional Training in Superadobe Intensive Workshop Series* was hosted at the Plenitud PR Center for Experiential Sustainability. Over the course of the five-week workshop, participants were given the chance to have a first-hand experience in superadobe construction, learning both the theory and the skills necessary to spearhead future superadobe construction, whether they be as part of a collective or through individual “D.I.Y.” builds. What made this workshop different from other courses offered in past was the level of immersion necessary to complete the curriculum objectives. COVID-19 restrictions that were in place during the time of training played a large part in how the dynamics of the workshop were designed. To achieve the construction of a superadobe dome, the professional training workshop educational model was organized starting with 1) two-week theoretical component; followed by 2) a three-week on-site building experience, for a total of five weeks. Over 50 people filled out registration forms, but due to the limited capacity allowed and the need to comply with COVID restrictions, only 10 participants who already lived in Puerto Rico were selected in the end.

During the first component a series of lectures and conferences were offered. Participants learned about the history of how superadobe as a technique was developed, the structural concepts of permaculture principles involved during the design process, how local material from Puerto Rico might be used as primary resources for these types of construction, and an overall list of basic equipment necessary to carry out a project. These conferences were offered virtually through platforms such as Zoom and Google Meets. This was designed as a strategy to have the participants fulfill the two-week quarantine required by COVID restrictions to be able to participate in-person for the on-site component; negative COVID tests results were presented prior to the on-site component. However, this also allowed the opportunity to open the virtual workshop to all those who submitted their application form that could not be selected for this workshop. As a result, lectures averaged at around 20 participants per class. Despite the limiting factors for the workshop, this educational model was able to adapt to extreme circumstances and make

opportunities like this to extend educational outreach for superadobe construction. This also allowed for more open networking dynamics between participants from different parts of Puerto Rico that might not have had the chance to meet had it not been for the online workshop component.

For the second component, the 10 selected participants had to arrive at a meeting site 20 minutes from the Plenitud PR's farm to begin their on-site training. During the first days of the on-site training, participants received a hands-on review of all the theoretical principles that were taught during the two-week virtual conference. Exercises included: construction of arches with adobe bricks, site planning, and placement of structure. For the remainder of the three weeks, participants traveled to Plenitud PR's farm to carry out the building for a superadobe dome designed for this course. The work scheduled was set Monday to Saturday from 7:00am to 3:00pm. In the initial exercises, participants had to build a small retaining wall. Through this exercise, participants got familiar with the process of digging a trench and creating footings for a superadobe structure, as well as learned the process of making the material mix and filling a bag. For the second exercise, participants had to complete small-scale domes that would serve as planters during site development. The purpose of this was to teach participants how to adapt the bag filling process on tighter circles when reaching the top of the dome without compromising the structural integrity of the ring. The third and final exercise was the construction of the dome itself. In this exercise, participants put into practice all the theoretical principles of superadobe (Figure 5). Construction of the dome was completed in 8 days. During construction, OSHA security measures were also applied during construction process such as: scaffolding standards, segregation of work areas, mixing stations, carpentry, and basic work gear as well as overall hydration and nutrition.

a) Two participants working on the final course of the dome.

b) Group of participants posing with the finished dome.

Figure 5: Participants of the *Professional Training in Superadobe Intensive Workshop*.

Through this exercise, participants also learned about plastering techniques that are used for superadobe construction specifically for Puerto Rico's climate conditions. In the same way COVID-19 restrictions limited the dynamics of the first component, it also created a unique opportunity for this second component. The dynamic of all 10 participants and two instructors staying in a separate location and having to travel to and from Plenitud PR's farm was designed to create a social bubble that allowed for the on-site workshop to happen without the worry of contracting COVID-19. As result, a strong community bond was formed amongst all 12 participants, creating a network of trained professionals superadobe builders prepared to spearhead future projects; it also projected a first look at a real superadobe construction team.

At the end of this five-week long workshop, participants received a certificate of completion sponsored by Plenitud PR in collaboration with Cal-Earth. This certification will open the door to a professional career in superadobe with which participants could join a work team or create ecological micro-businesses. The prospect of certification was one of the main incentives offered to participants. However, the certificate's biggest impact was the accessibility it offered those who have an interest in superadobe construction. Normally, participants would have to travel to California and participate in a weeklong training that would grant them a certificate directly from Cal-Earth. Following this route can prove to be very expensive and most people in Puerto Rico would not be able to afford it. Through the professional training workshop educational model, participants living in Puerto Rico could have a better access to the knowledge required to build superadobe structures with a more extensive workshop time, resulting in well-rounded professional builders.

Despite the heavy restrictions in place during the peak months of COVID-19 outbreaks, this educational model produced excellent results. With less restrictions, the same dynamics designed for this educational model could produce even stronger results. Despite the lack of widespread knowledge and mainstream appeal for superadobe projects, interest in superadobe is increasing as the newer generation of workers seeks a more affordable and sustainable option to build their homes. Demand for builders will increase and this educational model can serve as a solution for this demand.

CONCLUSIONS

As the climate crisis worsens, it is crucial to continue implementing adaptive solutions that both address the effects of the crisis and help reduce climate vulnerability for communities in Puerto Rico. It is imperative that these solutions consider all the factors that affect the archipelagos vulnerability, from solutions that address infrastructure robustness to those that help tackle socio-economic inequalities. In the context of the built environment, bioconstruction presents a variety of techniques and materials that can contribute to the safety of communities and their local economies. However, several challenges complicate the widespread implementation of these techniques like the lack of trained professionals in these techniques, clash with constructive culture and lack of permitting.

The nonprofit organization, Plenitud PR, has developed an educational model to advance the implementation of bioconstruction techniques on the island, particularly superadobe. The organization is tackling the challenges for implementation through educational outreach and programming. Two pathways have been developed: one for construction industry professionals and another for D.I.Y. builders. The goals of both pathways is to train more professionals in these techniques in how integrate them within the local construction culture. Several design and intensive training opportunities have been hosted by Plenitud PR, most notably the *Design in Bioconstruction Internship* in 2020 and the *Professional Training in Superadobe Intensive Workshop Series* in 2021.

Both workshops are critical examples of educational models that can be implemented to successfully address the existing resource gaps on bioconstruction on the island. The pathway for construction industry professionals demonstrates both a way to integrate these techniques within constructive cultures and close the legal and permitting gaps that negatively impact these projects. On the other hand, the pathway for D.I.Y. builders demonstrate a replicable model for training more builders and generating grassroots support for projects.

REFERENCES

- Aponte-González, F. (2013). Concerning Caribbean Climate Vulnerabilities and Adaptation in Small Island Cities. Manchester, United Kingdom.
- Belofsky, N., & Zemskova, K. (2018). Bringing Earthbags to the People - A New, Democratic Approach to Sustainable Building. *Consilience: The Journal of Sustainable Development*, 82-102.
- Canadell, S., Blanco, A., & Cavalaro, S. H. (2016). Comprehensive design method for earthbag and superadobe structures. *Materials and Design* 96, 270-282.
- Environmental Protection Agency. (2022). *Facility Level Information on Greenhouse Gases Tool*. Retrieved from EPA:
<https://ghgdata.epa.gov/ghgp/main.do#/facility/?q=Find%20a%20Facility%20or%20Location&st=PR&bs=&et=FC&fid=&sf=11001100&lowE=-20000&highE=23000000&g1=1&g2=1&g3=1&g4=1&g5=1&g6=0&g7=1&g8=1&g9=1&g10=1&g11=1&g12=1&s1=1&s2=1&s3=1&s4=1&s5=1&s6=1&s7=1&s8=1&s9=1&s>
- Hinojosa, J., & Meléndez, E. (2018). *The Housing Crisis in Puerto Rico and the Impact of Hurricane Maria*. New York, New York, USA: Center for Puerto Rican Studies at Hunter College. Retrieved from https://centropr-archive.hunter.cuny.edu/sites/default/files/data_briefs/HousingPuertoRico.pdf
- Kamal, R., & Rahman, S. (2018). A study on feasibility of super adobe technology-an energy efficient building system using natural resources in Bangladesh. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*.
- Khalili, N., & Vittore, P. (1998). Earth Architecture and Ceramics: The Sanbag/Superadobe/Superblock Construction System. *Building Standards*, 25-29.
- Lebron, G. E. (2020, March 14). Organización Plenitud PR promueve la bioconstrucción. *El Nuevo Día*.
- Murphy-Marcos, C., & Mazzei, P. (2022, January 31). The Rush for a Slice of Paradise in Puerto Rico. *New York Times*.
- ProAct network. (2008, August). *The Role of Environmental Management and Eco-Engineering in Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation*. Retrieved from PreventionWeb: https://www.preventionweb.net/files/4148_emecoengindrcca1.pdf
- Rodríguez, A. G., Rodrigues, M., & Sotomayor, O. (2019). Towards a sustainable bioeconomy in Latin America and the Caribbean: elements for a regional vision. *Natural Resources and Development series*.
- Rodríguez-Velázquez, V., & Sosa-Pascual, O. (2022, March 29). *Local and Federal Negligence Enables Environmental Crime in the Bahía Jobos Reserve*. Retrieved from <https://periodismoinvestigativo.com/2022/03/local-and-federal-negligence-enables-environmental-crime-in-the-bahia-jobos-reserve-in-salinas/>
- United States Census. (2021). *QuickFacts Puerto Rico*. Retrieved from United State Census Bureau: <https://www.census.gov/quickfacts/PR>

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.